

Effect of NPK levels on yield and yield-attributing characters of rice. Kashmir, India. 1990-91.

Nutrient level (kg ha ⁻¹)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	1,000-grain weight (g)
N				
40	4.0	318	57.8	21.25
80	4.5	331	65.8	21.70
120	4.7	339	69.0	23.05
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.37	5	1.7	0.50
P				
8.8	3.6	315	58.7	20.90
17.6	4.6	331	64.7	21.50
26.4	5.0	344	69.0	22.15
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.37	5	1.7	0.50
K				
16.6	4.9	322	63.0	21.40
33.2	5.5	335	65.4	21.65
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.30	4	1.3	0.40

Results showed that up to 80 kg of N and up to 26.4 kg of P ha⁻¹ significantly increased rice grain yield with concomitant improvement in all yield attributes (see table). The yield levels obtained were, however, lower than those of a timely sown crop (5.5 - 6.0 t ha⁻¹). This implies that a combination of 80-26.4-33.2 kg NPK ha⁻¹ will give satisfactory yields under late transplanting conditions in the valley. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Evaluating stem-nodulating green manure crops for lowland rice

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We studied the effect of stem-nodulating green manure (GM) crops *Sesbania rostrata*, *S. speciosa*, *Aeschynomene afraspera*, *A. indica*, *A. schemperi*, and *A. nilotica* on N₂ fixation and biomass production in lowland rice. The experiment was conducted during Aug 1993 and Jul 1994 wet season on a sandy loam acidic soil (pH 5.1) with 205 kg available N ha⁻¹. *S. aculeata* was the check.

Treatments were replicated four times in a randomized block design. The GM seeds were broadcast at 50 kg ha⁻¹ in all the 3 × 3-m plots. The GM plants were allowed to grow for 45 d after emergence; they were then cut at ground level from an area of 0.32 m² in each plot. N concentration of the whole plants was determined by micro-Kjeldahl method.

Significant differences in dry biomass production, N concentration, and N content of the GM crop were recorded (see table). *S. rostrata* and *A. afraspera* were found to be superior to all other species, indicating that these two are the most suitable GM crops for lowland rice soils. ■

Dry biomass production, N concentration, and N content of different green manure crops. Assam, India, 1993-94.

Species	Dry biomass (t ha ⁻¹)		N concentration (%)		N content (kg ha ⁻¹)	
	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i>	3.1	3.2	1.4	1.5	41	44
<i>Sesbania rostrata</i>	5.3	6.1	3.0	3.2	142	188
<i>Sesbania speciosa</i>	3.1	3.3	2.7	2.9	94	88
<i>Aeschynomene afraspera</i>	4.3	5.4	3.6	3.8	139	185
<i>Aeschynomene indica</i>	2.5	3.1	2.7	2.9	65	89
<i>Aeschynomene schemperi</i>	2.3	2.2	2.8	2.8	61	58
<i>Aeschynomene nilotica</i>	2.4	3.5	2.6	2.7	61	84
LSD (0.05)	2.5	2.3	1.8	1.9	30	32

Managing crop residue in rice

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Burning of crop leads to loss of organic matter and nutrients. Incorporating straw helps in nutrient recycling and maintains soil health. We carried out an experiment on crop residue management at GBPUAT, Pantnagar, during the 1993-94 kharif season.

Soil was loam with pH 7.4, 0.084% total N, 1.10% organic C, 17.0 kg available P ha⁻¹, and 194.0 kg available K ha⁻¹. The experiment, laid out in randomized block design, had 12 treatments with four replications, (see table).

Green manure (GM) crop *Sesbania aculeata* was grown and incorporated in the Same plot before transplanting rice, This provided 60 kg excess N ha⁻¹ in 1993 and 57 kg excess N ha⁻¹ in 1994. Berseem (*Trifolium alexandrinum* L.) was sown in a standing crop of rice at the milk stage and was incorporated in the field 1 mo before transplanting, giving an additional 80 and 70 kg N ha⁻¹ in the respective years. Incorporation of wheat straw, done without a starter dose, provided an additional 74 and 65 kg N ha⁻¹. With 20 kg of starter dose of N (as urea), straw incorporation provided